

IMMERSE D1.5_V3

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D1.5

IMMERSE Dashboard

VERSION 3.0

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Summary

Inventory of a set of 30 final indicators of integration that incorporates stakeholder's point of view and needs regarding these three variables (intercultural competences, psycho-social and gender). The dashboard has been elaborated from the theoretical framework developed in task 1.1, the workshops and interviews described in tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 selecting 50 indicators to be validated through a three-stages process resulting in a set of 30 consensuated indicators ecologically and empirically validated.

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Executive summary

The main objective of the IMMERSE project is to develop a dashboard of indicators about migrant children integration and provide representative data to impact policy making in the European context. This report provides the final dashboard of thirty indicators resulting from: a) the qualitative research inputs, b) the review of the literature and instruments and c) the content (Delphi study) and ecological (CARA methodology with stakeholders) validation process.

1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The aim of Task 1.6 is to implement the compilation and validation of the dashboard of indicators. In order to achieve this aim, Tasks 1.3, 1.4 and 1.5 were implemented to gather relevant qualitative data from the workshops and interviews. The leader team of WP1 provided the first set of indicators in light of these three variables in order to further elaborate an advanced dashboard of indicators of integration that incorporates stakeholder's point of view and needs regarding these three variables (intercultural competences, psycho-social and gender).

A set of 50 indicators were selected and validated through a three-stages process in order to finally select only 30 parameters considered most relevant for refugee and migrant children integration. This refinement was carried out by a content validation process consisting in a Delphi methodology and later a CARA methodology was implemented to ensure migrant children's voices are represented in the co-creation of the inventory of socio-educational integration indicators. The methodology of this process is explain in detail in the report for d1.6 on the results of the evaluation system of socio-educational integration of migrant children.

2 DASHBOARD OF INDICATORS

Table 1. Dashboard of indicators

#	FACTOR	FINAL VERSION	Reference source	Re-utilize	Data collection
1	01.2.1 Children's access to compulsory education	Scholarization rates. Proxied by: foreign children enrolled at school as a share of foreign children in compulsory ages <i>Note: we use citizenship (foreign children) as a proxy of migrant-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth) because data on school enrolment is more often available by citizenship than by migration-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth)</i> Source: administrative data and Eurostat	original	YES	
2	01.2.3 Children's access to health care	Difference in share of migrant-background and native respondents with children under 16 that	EU-SILC survey	YES	(children 10+)

		<p>had unmet needs for medical examination in the last 12 months</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Was there any time during the past 12 months when [any of] your child[ren] (aged 0-15) really needed medical examination or treatment (excluding dental examination or treatment)? Y/N [If yes] Did your child[ren] have a medical examination or treatment each time it was really needed? Y/N [If yes] What was the main reason for not having a medical examination or treatment? 1. Could not afford to (too expensive) 2. Waiting list or the time needed to obtain an appointment was too long 3. Could not take the time because of work, care of other children or of other persons 4. Too far to travel or no means of transportation 5. Other reason</p> <p>Source: EU-SILC survey (ad hoc module every 5 years, last in 2017).</p>			
<p>3</p>	<p>O2.1.1 Children's perceived competence in host language</p>	<p>Average score of migrant/background students in the survey items below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Imagine the following situations: A. You need to ask your teacher for some information in <main language>. Can you explain yourself? 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>B. When your teacher gives you some information in <main language>. Can you understand? 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows</p> <p>A. When I need to ask my teacher for some information in <main language> I can explain myself. 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>B. When my teacher gives me some information in <main language> I can understand. 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted for 6-9</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>O2.2.2 Children maintain their cultural identity while</p>	<p>Share of migrant background children picking the following combinations in the survey item below</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children 10+</p>

	<p>adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences</p>	<p>a. Some of 1-4; and also some of 5-7 b. Some of 1-4; and not 5-7 c. Some of 5-7; and not 1-4 d. Only options 8-10; none from 1-7</p> <p>A. Do you feel close to the following groups? (for example: groups of friends, classmates, neighbours, etc.) For each group: Y/N</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. People from your neighbourhood 2. People from [City where they live] 3. [People from Host country] (i.e. Germans, Irish, Spaniards...) 4. People working at your school (i.e. teachers, other employees...) 5. People from [children/parents' country/ies of origin*] 6. People with your same home language 7. People with your same religion 8. People of your same age 9. People of your same gender 10. People with your same interests and hobbies <p>B. Choose the three groups from question A to which you feel closest to and rank them 1st to 3rd:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 2. 3. <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be asked to children aged 6-9</u></p>			
<p>5</p>	<p>03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness</p>	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children that pick options 1-2 in survey item below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>In general, would you say you are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very happy 2 Quite happy 3 Not very happy 4 Not at all happy <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>	<p>EVS</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging</p>	<p>Average score in the survey items below among migrant-background children</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>How frequently do the following occur to you?</p> <p>For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p> <p>I feel like I belong at my school I can really be myself at school I feel like people at my school care about me</p>	<p>Student subjective wellbeing questionnaire (School connectedness subscale)</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p><i>Note: the selected indicator focuses on school belonging acknowledging the centrality of schools for the integration of migrant-children in general, and for their sense of belonging in the host country in particular</i></p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>		
7	04.1.1 Interconnectedness / Friends and peers	<p>A. Difference in the average score of migrant-background children and native children in the items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - My friends really try to help me - I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad - My friends stand up for me if someone mistreats me <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - My friends really try to help me - I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad - My friends stand up for me if someone is mean to me <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>	HBSC survey	Children, adapted 6-9
8	04.1.1 Interconnectedness / Friends and peers	<p>B. Share of all children (migrant-background and native) selecting option #4 in both survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many of your friends were born in a different country than yours? 1 All of them 2 The majority of them 3 A few 4 None</p>	Community Life Survey UK	Children 10+

		<p>5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>How many of your friends are from a different culture (beliefs, customs, traditions, ways of eating...)?</p> <p>1 All of them 2 The majority of them 3 A few 4 None 5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be asked to children 6-9</u></p>			
9	<p>04.1.2 Interconnectedness / Teachers</p>	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>How frequently do the following occur to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - My teachers really try to help me - Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - My teachers will stand up for me if someone mistreats me <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - My teachers really try to help me - Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - My teachers will stand up for me if someone is mean to me <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>	<p>ICCS survey</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>
10	<p>04.1.3 Interconnectedness / Institutions</p>	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>In [host country], do you trust the following?</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p>For each item: yes or no</p> <p>a. Teachers and schools</p> <p>b. Doctors and hospitals</p> <p>c. Police & justice system (judges, lawyers, courts, etc.)</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
11	05.1.1 Children's academic skills	<p>Difference in the share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science among migrant-background and native children (15-year-olds)</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Source: PISA</p>	PISA survey	YES	
12	05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education	<p>Share of persons with compulsory education completed among foreign-born population aged 16-20 who arrived in the host country before age 15</p> <p><i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Source: PIAAC</p>	PIAAC survey	YES	
13	05.2.2 Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels	<p>Difference in share of early leavers among foreign-born and non-foreign born persons aged 18-24</p> <p><i>Note: "Early leaver from education and training" refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has completed at most lower secondary education (<INSERT HERE THE CORRESPONDING LABEL IN YOUR NATIONAL EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM >) and is not involved in further education or training (formal or informal)</i></p> <p>Source: Eurostat/EU-LFS</p>	Eurostat/EU-LFS	YES	
14	05.2.3 Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	<p>Difference in share of foreign-born and non-foreign born population aged 16-24 who have completed (or are currently studying) upper secondary or tertiary studies in the survey country</p> <p><i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Source: PIAAC (2011/2, next in 2021/2; unavailable in Greece and French community in Belgium)</p>	PIAAC survey	YES	
15	D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status	<p>A. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Nationality</p> <p><i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167</i></p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES	

		<p><i>indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Nationality Strand aims to measure whether legal immigrants are encouraged to naturalise and whether their children born in the country are entitled to become full citizens. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions:</p> <p>D1. Eligibility (How long must migrants wait to naturalise? Are their children and grandchildren born in the country entitled to become citizens?) *</p> <p>D2. Conditions for acquisition (Are applicants encouraged to succeed through basic conditions for naturalisation?)*</p> <p>D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?) *</p> <p>D4. Dual nationality (Can naturalising migrants and their children be citizens of more than one country?) *</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/access-nationality</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 98. Residence period 99. Permits considered 100. Periods of prior-absence allowed 101. Requirements for spouses and partners (a. Spouses of nationals, b. partners of nationals, c. special exemptions) 102. Birth-right citizenship for second generation 103. Birth-right citizenship for third generation</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 104. Naturalisation language requirement (a. level, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 105. Naturalisation integration requirement (a. form, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 106. Economic resources 107. Criminal record 108. Good character 109. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 110. Maximum duration of procedure 111. Additional grounds for refusal 112. Discretionary powers in refusal 113. Legal protection 114. Protection against withdrawal of citizenship (a. grounds, time limits, statelessness protections)</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 115. Dual nationality for first generation (a. Renunciation requirement; b. Renunciation exemptions) 116. Dual nationality for second/third generation (at birth or before majority, facilitated, not facilitated)</p>			
16	D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning	B. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Permanent Residence	MIPEX policy indicators	YES	

	<p>(LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status</p>	<p><i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Permanent Residence aims to measure whether temporary legal residents have facilitated access to a long-term residence permit. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions:</p> <p>D1. Eligibility (Can all temporary legal residents apply for a long-term residence permit?)* D2. Conditions for acquisition (Do applicants for long-term residence have to fulfil the same basic conditions in society?)* D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?)* D4. Rights associated with status (Do long-term residents have the same residence and socio-economic rights?)*</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/permanent-residence</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 80. Residence period 81. Permits considered 82. Time counted as pupil/student 83. Periods of prior-absence allowed</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 84. Language requirement 85. Economic resources 86. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 87. Maximum duration of procedure 88. Duration of validity of permit 89. Renewable permit 90. Periods of absence allowed 91. Grounds for rejection, withdrawal, refusal 92. Personal circumstances considered before expulsion 93. Expulsion precluded 94. Legal protection</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 95. Access to employment 96. Access to social security and assistance 97. Access to housing</p>			
<p>17</p>	<p>D4.3 LPC access to education</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Access to Education" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

	<p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all children, with or without a legal status, have equal access to all levels of education *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators</p> <p>45. Compulsory education as legal right. Access is a legal right for all compulsory-age children in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals; 50 - Implicit obligation for all children (No impediment to equal access in law. e.g. No link between compulsory education and residence, or no category of migrant excluded); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants</p> <p>44. Access pre-primary and compulsory education: a. State-supported targeted measures (e.g. financial support, campaigns and other means) to increase participation of migrant pupils: b. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' successful completion of compulsory education (e.g. early school leaving/second chance programs). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support for all students (and targeted non-governmental initiatives where provided)</p> <p>46. Assessment of prior learning. The assessment in compulsory education of migrants' prior learning and language qualifications obtained abroad: a. Assessment with standardised quality criteria and tools; b. Requirement to use trained staff. Scores: 100- Both ; 50 - One; 0 - Case-by-case assessment by school staff without standardised criteria or training.</p> <p>47. Access to non-compulsory education is a legal right for all categories of migrants in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals; 50 - Certain categories of migrants do not have explicit access to certain levels (e.g. vocational training and apprenticeships); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants.</p> <p>48. Access to vocational training and training through apprenticeships or other work-based learning: a. Measures to specifically increase migrant pupil participation in such schemes (e.g. incentives); b. Measures to increase employers' supply of such schemes to migrant pupils (e.g. campaigns, support and guidance). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p> <p>49. Access to higher education: a. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' access to academic routes that lead to higher education;</p>			
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		<p>b. Targeted measures to increase acceptance and successful participation of migrant pupils (e.g. admission targets, additional targeted language support, mentoring, campaigns, measures to address drop-outs). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p>			
<p>18</p>	<p>D4.8 LPC access to health care</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Health <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Health Strand aims to measure whether the health system is responsive to immigrants' needs. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Entitlement to health services (Are health entitlements equal for immigrants and for nationals?) * D2. Policies to facilitate access (Do policies assist immigrants in accessing their health entitlements?) * D3. Responsive health services (Are health services adapting to become more responsive to immigrants' needs?) * D4. Measures to achieve change (Does government support health services to become more responsive to immigrants' needs?)*</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/health</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 151. Information for service providers about migrants' entitlements 152. Information for migrants concerning entitlements and use of health services (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out) 153. Information for migrants concerning health education and promotion (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out) 154. Provision of 'cultural mediators' or 'patient navigators' to facilitate access for migrants 155. Obligation and sanctions for assisting undocumented migrants (a. Obligation to report, b. Sanctions for helping)</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 145. Health entitlements for legal migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions) 146. Health entitlements for asylum seekers (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c.</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

		<p>special exemptions) 147. Health entitlements for undocumented migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions) 148. Administrative discretion and documentation for legal migrants 149. Administrative discretion and documentation for asylum seekers 150. Administrative discretion and documentation for undocumented migrants</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 156. Availability of qualified interpretation services (a. Cost/availability of interpreters, b. Methods of interpretation) 157. Requirement for 'culturally competent' or 'diversity-sensitive' services 158. Training and education of health service staff 159. Involvement of migrants in information provision, service design and delivery 160. Encouraging diversity in the health service workforce 161. Development of capacity and methods (a. Adapting methods, b. Specific methods)</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 162. Collection of data on migrant health 163. Support for research on migrant health 164. "Health in all policies" approach 165. Whole organisation approach 166. Leadership by government 167. Involvement of migrants and stakeholders (a. stakeholders, b. migrants)</p>			
19	<p>D3.7.1 Concentration in disadvantaged schools</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background students and native students enrolled in disadvantaged schools <i>Note: Disadvantaged schools are schools with a high concentration of students of low socio-economic status (25% or more, or 50% or more). The socio-economic status of families is the main predictor of educational disadvantage. Additionally, these schools tend to cumulate disadvantages (e.g. less resources, high teacher turnover, etc.). "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Source: survey data from PISA (15 years old), TIMSS (4th and 8th grade)</p>	original	YES	
20	<p>D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)</p>	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals) How important are the following aspects for this school? (please, consider how it is presented to parents that approach the school for the first time)</p>	original		Teachers & principals

		<p>For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias</p> <p>a. Educational excellence and/or results b. Educational innovation c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civiness, etc.)</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) How important are the following aspects for this school? For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias</p> <p>a. Educational excellence and/or results b. Educational innovation c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civiness, etc.)</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>			
21	<p>D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations</p>	<p>Average score in principals' answers to survey item below <i>Note: additionally, IMMERSE will collect information on parents' involvement in the same schools</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM (for principals) Does your school provide the following to students' parents? For each item: 1 No 2 Yes, generally for all parents 3 Yes, adapted for parents' needs (e.g. language, culture, etc.)</p> <p>a. Weekly (or more frequent) information on child's progress b. Requests and ideas to help students at home with homework c. Requests to volunteer and participate in school-related activities d. Channels to participate in decision-making</p> <p>Source: self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA.</p>	<p>self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA</p>		<p>Principals</p>
22	<p>D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally</p>	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals) Does the school curriculum include the following topics? For each item: Y/N</p> <p>Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity</p>	<p>PISA survey</p>		<p>Teachers & principals</p>

		<p>Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) In your lessons, do you include opportunities to promote the following skills? For each item: Y/N Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>			
<p>23</p>	<p>D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural education</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Intercultural Education For All" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all pupils and teachers are supported to learn and work together in a diverse society *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators: 60. School curriculum to reflect diversity. The official aims of intercultural education include the appreciation of cultural diversity, and is delivered: a. As a stand-alone curriculum subject; b. Integrated throughout the curriculum. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Intercultural education not included in curriculum, or intercultural education does not include appreciation of cultural diversity 62. Adapting curriculum to reflect diversity. The school curricula and teaching materials can be modified to reflect changes in the diversity of the school population: a. State guidance on curricular change to reflect both national and local population variations; b. Inspection, evaluation and monitoring of implementation of (a). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One of these; 0 - None. 61. State support for public information initiatives to promote the appreciation of cultural diversity throughout society. Scores: 100 - Initiatives part of mandate of state-subsidised bod; 50 - Initiatives part of state budget line for ad hoc funding; 0 - Neither 63. Adapting daily school life to reflect diversity. Daily life at school can be adapted based on cultural or religious needs in order to avoid exclusion of pupils, which might include one or a few of the following: changes to the existing school timetable and religious holidays; educational activities; dress codes and clothing;</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

		<p>school menus. Scores: 100 - State regulations or guidelines concerning local adaptation; 50 - Law allows for local or school-level discretion; 0 - No specific adaptation foreseen in law.</p> <p>64. Teacher training to reflect diversity. Teacher training and professional development programmes require intercultural education and the appreciation of cultural diversity for all teachers: a. topic in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. topic in obligatory in-service professional development training. Scores: 100 - Both A and B required; 50 - Both offered extensively; 0 - only ad hoc/ project basis</p>			
24	D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes	<p>Whether there are provisions of preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students at state or national level <i>Note: Preparatory classes – in some countries also referred to as 'reception classes' or 'transition classes' – are separate classes or lessons in which newly arrived migrant students are provided with intensive language teaching and, in some cases, an adapted curriculum for other subjects with the intention of preparing them to integrate into mainstream classes. Students may be placed in these classes/lessons full time or combine these classes/ lessons with mainstream ones (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017).</i></p> <p>Source: Eurydice 2019 and subsequent reports.</p> <p>We will cross-check, complement and update this data with survey data collected by IMMERSE from principals (survey item below).</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Are there provisions or recommendations at the regional or national level to offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes, at national level 2 Yes, at regional level 3 Yes, at both national and regional levels 4 No</p> <p>Does this school offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes 2 No</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE).</p>	Eurydice 2019	YES	(Principals)
25	D4.16.2 LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Targeting needs" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether migrant children, as well as their parents and</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES	

		<p>teachers, are entitled to have their specific needs addressed in school *</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators:</p> <p>50. Educational guidance. Access to advice and guidance on system and choices at all levels of compulsory and non-compulsory education (pre-primary to higher): a. Written information on educational system in migrant languages of origin; b. Provision of resource persons/centres for orientation of migrant pupils; c. Provision of interpretation services for families of migrant pupils for general educational advice and guidance at all levels. Scores: 100 - All three ; 50 - one or two; 0 - Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives.</p> <p>51. Provision of support to learn language of instruction (average 51a-51c)</p> <p>51a. Language instruction. Provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils: a. In compulsory education (both primary and secondary); b. In pre-primary education. Note: Migrant pupils may be placed in the mainstream classroom or a separate classroom for a transitional phase. This question relates to language support in either case. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - No provision. Only through private or community initiatives</p> <p>51b. Communicative/academic fluency. Provision includes: a. Communicative literacy (general fluency in reading, writing, and communicating in the language); b. Academic literacy (fluency in studying, researching, and communicating in the language in the school academic setting). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Level/goals not specified or defined</p> <p>51c. Language instruction standards. Provision includes quality measures: a. Requirement for courses to use established second-language learning standards; b. Requirement for teachers to be specialised and certified in these standards; c. Curriculum standards are monitored by a state body. Scores: 100 - Two or more of these; 50 - At least one; 0 - None of these</p> <p>52. Migrant pupil monitoring. Policy on pupil monitoring targets migrants. Scores: 100 - System disaggregates migrants into various sub-groups, e.g. gender, country of origin; 50 - System monitors migrants as a single aggregated group; 0 - None. Migrants are only included in general categories for monitoring that apply to all students.</p> <p>53. Targeted policies to address educational situation of migrant groups: a. Systematic provision of guidance (e.g. teaching assistance, homework support); b. Systematic provision of financial resources. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0</p>		
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		<p>- None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through voluntary initiative</p> <p>54. Teacher training and professional development programmes require courses that address migrant pupils' learning needs, teachers' expectations of migrant pupils, and specific teaching strategies to address this: a. Topic required in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. Topic required in obligatory in-service professional development training.</p> <p>Scores: 100 - Both required; 50 - Both offered extensively to teachers; 0 - only on ad hoc / project basis.</p>			
<p>26</p>	<p>D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/ language support</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there services in your school providing learning support for students after school hours (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.)? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there services in your <community / neighbourhood> providing learning support for students (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.) ? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Do you take any classes at school to help you with your schoolwork or learn new languages, but are not part of your normal school day (after class)? 1 Yes, I do take classes 2 My school has those, but I don't take classes 3 No, my school doesn't have those 4 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Do you take any classes (outside of school) in your neighbourhood (where you live) to help you</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p>with school work or learn new languages ? 1 Yes, I do take classes 2 My neighbourhood (the place I live in) has those, but I don't take classes 3 No, my neighbourhood (the place I live in) doesn't have those 4 I don't know</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
<p>27</p>	<p>D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your community / neighbourhood? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there are no such services at all 4 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your community / neighbourhood? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there are no such services at all 4 I don't know</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

28	D3.6.2 Counselling services at school	<p>Share of schools with some staff dedicated to psycho-social support or personal counselling, based on survey item below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many staff does your school currently have in the following capacities? Please note this refers to staff hired specifically to conduct these tasks, which usually requires some specific training. For each category: Nr full time: __ Nr part time: ____</p> <p>a. Language support teachers b. Learning support teachers (exclude the ones counted in a.) c. Psycho-social support / personal counselling d. Academic counselling / guidance (exclude the ones counted in c.)</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE)</p>	original		
29	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	<p>B. Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who answer positively to survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do you ever avoid certain places (such as shops, cafes, public transportation, some particular neighbourhood, some places in school) for fear of being treated badly? Y/N/Sometimes</p> <p>IF YES OR SOMETIMES Is the reason for this related to any of the issues below? (multiple option)</p> <p>1 Your culture (traditions, customs...) 2 Your race, ethnicity (i.e. skin colour...) 3 Your religion 4 Your gender (male/female/other) 5 Your sexual orientation (the gender(s) you are attracted to) 6 Your age 7 Your social class 8 Other</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be applied to children aged 6-9.</u></p>	Based on EU-MIDIS and original follow-up		Children 10+
30	D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children responding 2-5 in the survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p>			

		<p>Have you ever been bullied in [host country] by schoolmates at your school, your neighbourhood or online?</p> <p>1 No, never 2 It has happened to me a few times 3 It has happened to me many times</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>			
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